

MATLAB main code- Simultaneous analysis of blood flow and diameter on mesenteric arteries *in vivo*

This code computes the blood flow and diameter from a series of images (in *.jpg format) obtained using a laser speckle imaging system (RFLSI III).

The source code has been separated into sections to delineate the different parts of the code. The green text indicates a comment.

The code starts here.

Set the working directory to the location of your input image sequence and input the sample rate.

```
clc
clear all
close all

corePath = uigetdir;
if isequal(corePath,0)
    disp('User selected: Cancel');
else
    disp(['User selected:', corePath]);
end
imageFiles=dir([corePath '*.jpg']);
nfiles= length(imageFiles); % total number of images

sampleRate=2; % Modify this line to change the sample rate. Time is in seconds.
Total_time=sampleRate*nfiles;
time=linspace(0,Total_time,nfiles);
```

Input the desired number of segments (arterial branches) to analyze.

```
HomeI=imread(fullfile(corePath, '1.jpg'));% Read the 1st image (Home image)
prompt=['How many segments are you going to select?' ''];% Input No. of desired ROIs
str = input(prompt,'s');
Num_segment= str2num(str);% Number of ROIs selected
ROIS_pos=zeros(Num_segment,4);% Matrix of selected ROIs positions
```

Draw the desired ROIs on the arterial branches that will be analyzed.

```
[ROIS_pos] = ROI_SELECTION(HomeI,Num_segment);  
[rectangle2]=LAST_IMAGE(nfiles,Num_segment, corePath, ROIS_pos);% This is to verify  
that there was no movement in the region recorded during the course of the experiment  
pause(1)
```

This is the main section of the code. Here, the diameter calculation and blood flow (flux) are performed.

```
Diameter=zeros(Num_segment,nfiles);% In pixels  
Flux1=zeros(Num_segment,nfiles); % arbitrary units  
  
    for i=1:Num_segment  
  
        ROIN=ROIS_pos(i,:);  
        for ii=1:nfiles  
Status=['Analyzing' ' ' 'Segment' ' ' num2str(i) '...']  
        ii  
  
        [I_crop, Total_pix]=CROPPING_IMAGE(ii,corePath, ROIN);  
  
        [Red_gray]=Gray_conversion2(I_crop);  
  
        [BW_MASK]=BINARY_MASK(Red_gray);  
  
        Check_ones=find(BW_MASK);  
        L_check_ones=length(Check_ones);  
  
        [meanDiameter]=DIAMETER_CALCULATION(BW_MASK,Check_ones,i,ii, Diameter);  
        [meanIntensity1]=FLUX_CALCULATION3(BW_MASK,L_check_ones, Red_gray, Total_pix);  
        Diameter(i,ii)=meanDiameter;  
        Flux1(i,ii)=meanIntensity1;  
end  
  
end
```

Here each arterial segment trace is plotted. Diameter and Flux as a function of time (seconds)

```
prompt2=['Introduce a title for the graphic:' ''];% Set a title to the results plot.
title_name = input(prompt2,'s');
```

```
for k=1:Num_segment
```

```
    Sm_Diameter=smooth(time,Diameter(k,:),0.04, 'loess'); %Trace smoothing
    Sm_Diameter=transpose(Sm_Diameter);
    Sm_Flux1=smooth(time,Flux1(k,:),0.06, 'loess'); %Trace smoothing
    Sm_Flux1=transpose(Sm_Flux1);
    figure
    [AX, H1, H2]=plotyy(time,Sm_Diameter,time,Sm_Flux1); %Create graph with two y-axes
    set(get(AX(1),'YLabel'),'String','Diameter
(a.u.)','FontSize',14,'FontWeight','bold','Color','b');
    set(get(AX(1),'YAxis'),'FontSize',12,'FontWeight','bold','Color','b');
    set(H1,'LineWidth',1.5,'Color','b');
    set(get(AX(1),'XAxis'),'FontSize',12,'FontWeight','bold','Color','k');

    set(get(AX(2),'Ylabel'),'String','Blood Flow
(a.u.)','FontSize',14,'FontWeight','bold','Color','r');
    set(get(AX(2),'YAxis'),'FontSize',12,'FontWeight','bold','Color','r');
    set(H2,'LineWidth',1.5,'Color','r');

    legend('Diameter','Flux')
    title(sprintf(' Segment %d %s',k,title_name));
    xlabel('Time (Seconds)', 'FontSize',14, 'FontWeight','bold');

    print((sprintf(' Segment %d %s',k,title_name)),'-depsc','-tiff')%
    print((sprintf(' Segment %d %s',k,title_name)),'-djpeg','-r0')%

end
open Diameter% Matrix variable where the Diameter values are stored.
open Flux1% Matrix variable where the flux values are stored.
```

MATLAB functions- Simultaneous analysis of blood flow and diameter on mesenteric arteries *in vivo*

This code computes the blood flow and diameter from a series of images (in *.jpg format) obtained using a laser speckle imaging system (RFLSI III).

The following MATLAB functions are called from the main code. The green text indicates a comment.

Function: ROI_SELECTION

```
function [ROIS_pos] = ROI_SELECTION(A,Num_segment)
figure(1)
imshow(A)
title('Home Image')
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
Segment=1;
selection_on=1;
while selection_on==1
rectangle=drawrectangle('Label', num2str(Segment), 'Color',[1 0
0],'InteractionsAllowed', 'none');
ROIS_pos(Segment,:)=rectangle.Position;
if Segment==Num_segment
selection_on=0;
end
Segment=Segment+1;
end

end
```

Function: LAST_IMAGE.

```
function [rectangle2]=LAST_IMAGE(nfiles,Num_segment, corePath, ROIS_pos)
last_file=[num2str(nfiles) '.jpg'];
B=imread(fullfile(corePath, last_file));

for n=1:Num_segment
figure(2)
imshow(B)
title('Last Image')
```

```
        rectangle2=drawrectangle('Label', num2str(n), 'Color', [1 0
0], 'Position', ROIS_pos(n,:), 'InteractionsAllowed', 'none');
        hold on
    end
```

```
end
```

Function: CROPPING_IMAGE.

```
function [I_crop, Total_pix]=CROPPING_IMAGE(ii,corePath, ROIN)
```

```
    name_file= [num2str(ii) '.jpg'];
    currentfilename= fullfile(corePath,name_file);
    currentimage = imread(currentfilename);
    I_crop=imcrop(currentimage,ROIN);
    [R C Ch]=size(I_crop);
    Total_pix=R*C;
```

```
end
```

Function: Gray_conversion2.

```
function [Red_gray]=Gray_conversion2(I_crop)
```

```
    I = rgb2ycbcr(I_crop);
    R=I_crop(:,:,1);
    G=I_crop(:,:,2);
    B=I_crop(:,:,3);
```

```
    Y=0.4*R+0.4*G+0.2*B;
```

```
    Y2=im2double(Y);
```

```
    Red_gray=Y2;
```

```
end
```

Function: BINARY_MASK.

```
function [BW_MASK]=BINARY_MASK(Red_gray)
se = strel('diamond',3);
Red_BW=(Red_gray);
Red_BW=imfill(Red_BW, 'holes');
Red_BW=imclose(Red_BW, se);
Check_1s=find(Red_BW);
if isempty(Check_1s)
    BW_MASK=Red_BW;
else
    imag_bw_label=bwlabel(Red_BW);
    propiedades=regionprops(imag_bw_label);
    Areas=vertcat(propiedades.Area);
    Max_area=max(Areas);
    BW_MASK=bwareaopen(imag_bw_label,Max_area);
end
end
```

Function: DIAMETER_CALCULATION.

```
function [meanDiameter]=DIAMETER_CALCULATION(BW_MASK,Check_ones,i,ii, Diameter)

if isempty(Check_ones)
    meanDiameter=Diameter(i, ii-1);
else

BW3=~BW_MASK;
edtImage=bwdist(BW3);
skelImage=bwskel(BW_MASK, 'MinBranchLength',20);
Check_branch=length(find(skelImage));
a=5;
while Check_branch==0
    min_branch=20-a;
    skelImage=bwskel(BW_MASK, 'MinBranchLength',min_branch);
    Check_branch=length(find(skelImage));
    a=a+5;
end
```

```
meanRadius=mean(edtImage(skelImage));
meanDiameter=2*meanRadius;
end
end
```

Function: FLUX_CALCULATION3.

```
function [meanIntensity1]=FLUX_CALCULATION3(BW_MASK,L_check_ones, Red_gray,Total_pix)
if L_check_ones<0.03*Total_pix;
    low_thresholds=find(Red_gray>0.1138);
    if isempty(low_thresholds)
        meanIntensity1=mean(mean(Red_gray))*255;
    else
        Intensity=Red_gray(low_thresholds);
        meanIntensity1=mean(Intensity)*255;
    end
else
    Intensity= Red_gray(BW_MASK);
    meanIntensity1=mean(Intensity)*255;
end
end
```